

INFLUENCE OF URBANISATION ON EMPLOYMENT OPPORTUNITIES OF THE URBAN DWELLERS IN ENUGU STATE

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Abstract: The study determined the Influence of Urbanisation on Employment Opportunities of the Urban Dwellers in Enugu State. Specifically, the study sought to: determine the influence of increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state, evaluate the influence of concentration of development activities in urban centres on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state and ascertain the influence of the existence of higher education on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. The study was guided by three research questions and hypotheses. The study adopted a survey design. The researcher made use of primary and secondary data sources. The population of the study was 1,481,552. The sample size of 576 was determined through the use of the Freud & William formula. A Chi-square test was used to test the hypotheses. The finding revealed that an increased population rate has a significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state, the Concentration of development activities in urban centres has a significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state and the existence of higher education has a significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. The study concluded that the high population growth rate, the concentration of development activities in urban centres, Existence of higher education influenced urban unemployment significantly. The study recommended that the government of Enugu State should make provisions for the rapid development of rural communities, as this will help to reduce rural-urban migration and control the high population growth rate in urban areas.

Keywords: Urbanisation, Employment, Opportunities, Development and Urban Dwellers

1.1 Introduction

Rapid urbanisation is taking place over the world, particularly in emerging countries, where over half of the inhabitants is expected to be urban by 2020. (UN, 2015). A movement in population distribution from dispersed rural areas to more compact towns or cities, as well as the movement of a continuous-increasing labor force from agriculture to the non-agricultural area, are the fundamental components of urbanisation, which is often accompanied by a change in lifestyle (Wizor & Anthony, 2020). The process of urbanisation entails a shift in labor from traditional to contemporary sectors. As a result, the employment of laborers is an important topic in urban studies. Wage earners and self-employed people are the two sorts of workers, and employment stability is divided into two categories: steady wage labour and casual work (Olawajaju & Oviasogie) (2019). Urbanisation is a process, and it is important to remember that the transfer of workers from the agricultural to non-agricultural sectors is limited not only by personal characteristics, but also by the capacity of non-agricultural enterprises (Ahmed and Suleman) (2018). As a result, employment is tightly linked to non-agricultural sector development,

particularly industrial development. Despite the fact that urbanisation is a spatial consequence of economic expansion, policymakers must recognize that cities must be treated as a priority in order to accomplish the broader goals of sustainable development and inclusive growth (Unah, 2021).

Unah and Ibrahim (2019), are of the view that one of the most vital roles that cities can have in economic development is the creation of extra and better jobs; however, creating better jobs appears to have fallen to the bottom of the global urban agenda, even when there is a clear link between urban services and job creation. In the developing world, there isn't much of a link between urbanization, industrialization, and the rise of formal employment. The connection between urbanization and the creation of jobs, especially in the form of productive, formal employment– is complex and ambiguous; urbanisation is often used as a one-size-fits-all proxy for increasing economic opportunities (Unah & Muktar, 2020). High birth rates, accompanied by unemployment and a low standard of living in rural areas, resulted in a steady inflow of people to cities, where possibilities abound, such as appealing jobs, better education, and a contemporary lifestyle, resulting in a very dynamic growth process (Ozei, Sezgin & Topkaya, 2013). Urbanization is speeding up in both developed and developing nations. Fast urbanization, especially the growth of large cities, as well as the issues of unemployment, poverty, inadequate health care, poor sanitation, urban slums, and environmental degradation that accompany it, pose a significant challenge to developing nations (Ahmed & Suleman, 2018).

Urbanization, which entails an increase in the number of people residing in urban areas within a particular year, is the process of moving from a rural to an urban civilization (Adetunji and Oyeleye, 2013). Growing urbanization and demographic changes have significant effects on employment, food, security, water supply, housing, and sanitation, particularly the removal of solid and liquid waste generated by cities (Olaleye, 2013). The concern is whether the recent development in urban growth is sustainable, especially in emerging nations, given the attendant urban challenges of unemployment, poverty, and environmental degradation. Unah (2021), says that there is still a lack of public infrastructure and services in residential neighborhoods. Urbanization is said to be crucial to development because it not only produces a modern state but also opens doors for reducing urban poverty, promoting sustainable development, encouraging smaller families and family planning, raising standards of living, extending life expectancy, and producing a large number of job opportunities.

However, owing to negative environmental repercussions and other negative outcomes associated with excessive resource consumption and inadequate management, urbanization can constitute a substantial challenge to achieving sustainable economic development. While urbanization aidsto generate economic riches for the country and raises living standards for the urban population, it also puts a significant strain on city infrastructure and contributes to difficulties linked with a loss in employment prospects, it is frequently said. Enugu has faced significant urbanization challenges, including rapid population expansion, overcrowding, the spread of slums, rising traffic and industrial pollution, overused urban infrastructure, and urban poverty, all of which have resulted in a slew of environmental, economic, and cultural matters. Given this backdrop that the study justifies the study of the Influence of urbanization on employment opportunities in Enugu State.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Urbanization, often known as the growth and expansion of cities, has long been acknowledged as a catalyst for economic prosperity.

Urban areas have a huge potential for economic growth and poverty reduction due to the concentration of large-scale manufacturing economies and industries.

The relationship between urbanization and growth is evident in the fact that urban areas serve as important financial hubs and investment destinations, attracting higher investments in infrastructure and human capital as a result of the concentration of institutions of higher learning that support research and development and, in turn, the growth of numerous industries. Additional employment opportunities are produced as a result of increasing investment, resulting in increased income, expenditure, and growth. As a result of the rapid increase of economic activity in Enugu State, urbanization is supposed to create job possibilities, however this has not been the case.

The influx of people and quick population expansion to Enugu city, which is aimed at improving positive survival and self-fulfillment, has certain consequences in the destinations. The strategy of concentrating development activities in Enugu city may encourage rural-urban migration, resulting in chronic unemployment in the city center. The high unemployment rate in urban areas contributes to metropolitan poverty. Individuals are drawn to metropolitan areas by the expanding number of private and public educational institutions in Enugu, implying a severe economic effect with widespread unemployment. If urbanization is not accompanied by good planning and control, it will result in unemployment, which will have an impact on the economic structure of most urban families. Children will be seen hawking in various streets as a way of contributing to their family's economic source rather than attending school like the majority of their peers.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study was to examine the influence of urbanization on employment opportunities in Enugu State. The specific objectives include the following:

1. Determine the influence of the increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.
2. Evaluate the influence of concentration of development activities in urban centres on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.
3. Ascertain the influence of the existence of higher education on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

1.4 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the work:

1. What is the influence of the increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?
2. What influence has the concentration of development activities in urban centres on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?
3. What is the influence of higher education on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the study:

1. The increased population rate has no significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.
2. The concentration of development activities in urban centres has no significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.
3. The existence of higher education has no significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

1.6 Significance of the Study

The significance of this study is as follows:

Theoretically, the study will be reference material for the students of Public Administration and Urban Development Administration.

Policy Makers: In many aspects, Nigeria's economic and social progress depends heavily on this study. First, if it is determined that population increase is the only factor driving Nigeria's unemployment rate upward continuously, the government will be urged to step up population control efforts, notably in the areas of contraceptives and family planning.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The coverage of this study was to evaluate the influence of urbanization on Employment Opportunities of Urban dwellers in Enugu state. The study evaluated various urbanization indices as it affects employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state; it covered urban dwellers in Enugu South, Enugu East, Enugu North, Nkanu West, Oji River, Nsukka and Udenu Government Areas.

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.1 Urbanization

The environmental development of rural or natural land into urban areas as a result of immigration, according to Wikipedia's definition from 2016. While the United Nations defines it as a migration of individuals from rural to urban regions as a result of population expansion (Unah & Muktar, 2020). The clustering of people into a relatively big number at a certain location on the earth's surface is characterized as urbanization. Thus, in industrialized countries, Urbanization, as opposed to agglomeration of people, which is typically the result of rural-urban drift, is the result of fast development, modernization, and industrialization. Nigeria's urbanization, like that of the majority of developing nations, is a result of the rural areas' "push" and the urban centers' "pull" (Unah & Ibrahim, 2019). The population is the source of the push and pull in this regard, which may be traced back to the consequences of regional imbalances.

Urbanization is a socioeconomic phenomenon that causes people to shift and migrate, particularly the working class, to more economically viable cities. Demographers describe urbanisation like the growing magnitude of the population living in cities (Poston & Bouvier, 2010). Urbanization, according to Mabogunje (2012), is a process of agglomeration in a multi-functional human community of a significant scale. According to this definition, urbanization is the process that refers to the growth in size and number of urban areas; urbanization is the process that relates to the expansion of the total people resident in an urban region.

2.1.1.1 Population growth

The increase in the number of people living in a country, state, county, or city is known as population growth. A significant market for goods and services will emerge as the population grows. When there are a lot of people, there is a lot of demand for goods and services. There will be a huge number of possible customers. Food, clothing, and shelter will be in higher demand. Furthermore, there will be an increase in the demand for children's materials. A significant number of children is always present in a fast developing population (Ogunsola, 2016).

2.1.1.2 Concentration of Development Activities in Urban Centres

Urban Development encompasses the social, cultural, environmental, economic, and physical development and management of a city, as well as Urban Planning, Human Settlements development, and Urban Sustainability implementation. Urban development refers to non-rural development that varies from rural development in terms of size, intensity, visual character, and the prominence of built structures. Urbanization, as opposed to agglomeration of people, which is typically the result of rural-urban drift, is the result of fast development, modernization, and industrialization. Nigeria's urbanization, like that of the majority of developing nations. Urban centers are described as areas with a diverse range of economic undertakings that provide fundamental human services, social services, and physical development (Adejomo, 2018). High population densities are also a feature of urban areas, with people inhabiting every economic sector of the metropolis.

2.1.1.3 Rapid growth of formal education

Formal education is a structured educational system that includes specialized vocational, technical, and professional training programs and runs from primary (and in some countries, nursery) school through university. Formal education frequently leads to recognition and certification. Educational growth refers to how much pupils improve their skills as they progress through the educational system. A trend is a pattern formed over time by similar group results. Teachers, education policymakers, and policy analysts need to know about growth and trends. Zaid (2016), states that a number of variables such as population growth, educational expansion, and the rise of the middle class have contributed to an increase in demand for university spots. In addition, the continual growth of communication and information technology has provided experienced individuals with new requirements, allowing universities to create and expand promising study topics. As a result of the growing competitiveness in the educational market as a result of technological and informational advancements, universities are seeking to attract an increasing number of students interested in these subjects. It is necessary to emphasize that the quality of educational processes and services are the defining elements for the growth, success,

and sustainability of higher education institutions, representing the strategic, effective, and complete factor of any university administration.

2.1.2 Employment Opportunity

Hire, relocation, promotion, training, and non-disciplinary retention are all instances of employment opportunities, which include any restructuring or layoff. Employment opportunities do not imply the formation of a post or specialized training not previously available to other employees. Policymakers in Nigeria recognized job creation for full employment as a vital mechanism for aligning economic growth with the country's developmental requirements early on. One of the cardinal aims of the First National Development Plan (FNDP) (1962-68) was to provide employment possibilities that would be accessible to all inhabitants. Nigeria's growing unemployment rate has become the bane of the country's economic prosperity. "The increased incidence of social ills among young people is due to joblessness."

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author’s Conceptualization, 2022.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

2.2.1. Push-Pull Theory

Ernest Ravenstein's push-pull theory lies at the heart of this study (1989). One of the early migration theorists, Ernest Ravenstein, used census data from England and Wales to demonstrate why individuals migrate from one place to another. He emphasized in his book "Law of Migration" that unfavorable conditions in rural areas "push" people away from their permanent residences and "pull" them into temporary or permanent residences. Heavy taxation, high temperatures, educational opportunities, unhealthy agricultural goods, floods, and starvation were some of the push variables investigated.

Free movement, a tranquil atmosphere, good land, lower taxes, and career opportunities, on the other hand, are all pull factors (Ravenstein, 1989).

According to Ravenstein's migration theory, Enugu city centres, which were formerly a traditional civilization, had 'pull' elements that drew people from all over the world. Although the circumstances that led to this settlement were not necessarily negative, the environment had been expedited by the British colonial authority, which gave work possibilities, excellent educational facilities, a pleasant atmosphere, and brisk trade and commerce (Eyeh, 2015a, 2015b) Thus, the pull element must be considered in order to completely comprehend Enugu's urban experiences for migrants. In the Enugu city, the British colonial infrastructure was established: schools, courts, police stations, hospitals, and churches.

These opportunities for settlers and indigenous people have led to the employment of clerks, interpreters, cleaners, errand boys, and schoolboys, among other occupations. These laborers told their family the good news after eventually settling in Enugu through one vocational job.

To satisfy the demands and expectations of the hordes of civil workers, those lacking the knowledge required for colonial employment turned to trading. One of West Africa's largest markets is presently located in Enugu. Equally important are the push factors that led individuals away from their traditional vocations of farming and livestock husbandry and toward those of daily wage employees and tax-paying adults. In addition to a monetized economy, the newly conquered environment required all adult males to pay tax. Men could only receive earnings in the currency in Enugu's urban centers, which allowed them to pay taxes and avoid the risk of being imprisoned if they defaulted. The Enugu metropolis was also a big construction site, with many government buildings sprouting up; laborers were needed, and news of opportunities to earn daily pay and make progress in the new places seeped into the hinterland.

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 High Population Growth Rate and Employment opportunity

In Ikare Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria, Adejomo (2018) conducted a study on urbanization and unemployment. The data was analyzed using theme analysis, and the study used a descriptive research design. The study found that urbanization is widespread, and that urbanization is one of the leading causes of unemployment. Infrastructure, trade and commerce, political causes, and the high birth rate are also other indicators of urbanisation. The study also found that socio-cultural variables, poor technology, weather conditions, and government regulations are all factors that contribute to unemployment. According to the findings, urbanisation has a negative impact on employment opportunities, infrastructure, and housing, while it has a positive impact on crime rates.

Emodi and Emeka (2018) investigated how urbanization has influenced biodiversity in the Enugu metropolitan. The respondents' perceptions of how urbanization has harmed biodiversity in the area were assessed utilizing descriptive statistics like frequency distribution and percentage. In general, respondents believed that urbanization's drawbacks included population pressure, deforestation, pollution, and soil degradation. As a result, the study discovered that some wildlife and flora have suffered as a result of urbanization. As a result of habitat degradation, some species are in danger of extinction or threatened, and some have even gone extinct.

Ademu (2015) conducted a similar study on the Urbanization Problem and the Challenge of Youth Unemployment in Nigerian Cities. The research looked at the issue of urbanization and youth unemployment in Nigerian cities. In its analysis, the study takes an analytical approach.

The report stated that governments, in addition to rallying stakeholders in the economy to engage in job-creating possibilities, must be directly involved in job creation.

Iyi (2014) conducted an urban growth and development review in Enugu (Enugu State, Nigeria). In the study, a survey research design was used. The data acquired throughout the investigation was analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The study found that the identified markers have just a weak association. The progression from the starting places to other areas was brisk at first, but decreased in later years. The slow pace of development was highlighted as a result of a lack of focus on newer ideas to meet the ever-growing population of people and automobiles.

2.3.2 Concentration of Development Activities in urban centres and Employment opportunity

Ahmed and Suleman (2018) used annual data from 1980 to 2016 to investigate the impact of urbanization on economic growth in Nigeria, utilizing a limits testing technique to cointegration. The empirical inquiry began with Auto Dicky Fuller and Phillips-Perron unit root tests. The outcomes of the unit tests revealed that the series' integration order is a combination of I(1) and I(2) (2). The findings of the ARDL bounds testing revealed that GDP, unemployment, population, and fixed capital formation had a long-run relationship. In the short run,

urbanization has a favorable and considerable impact on GDP, but this is not the case in the long run. In the long run, population growth also appeared to be favorable and highly associated to economic growth.

Chukwuedozie and Ignatius (2014) investigated the influence of rural-urban migration on rural livelihoods in Nigeria's southeast. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, the Livelihood Asset Indices approach, and Principal Component Analysis. The findings revealed that the impact of migration on livelihoods varies across the region.

Wondimagegnu (2012) investigated the effects of rural-urban migration on rural households' income and poverty in Shebedino district, Southern Ethiopia. The study used both primary and secondary data in a survey research design. A Cobb-Douglas production function model was then used, and descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to analyze the data. The study's conclusions showed that while migration has decreased the amount of labor that is available in rural areas, remittances have a favorable and significant impact on promoting capital stock investment. In general, rural-urban mobility increased the total farm income of migrant-sending households.

2.3.3 Growth of Formal Education and Employment opportunity

Wizor and Le-ol (2020) worked in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, on Urbanization and Its Effects on Housing for the Urban Poor. A descriptive statistical method was used to analyze the respondents' responses. A descriptive statistical method was used to analyze the respondents' responses. According to the findings of the inquiry, the bulk of the flats inhabited by the urban poor in Uyo metropolitan are single rooms and self-contained, and they are typically overcrowded. Kidnapping (8.5%), pickpocketing (22.4%), robbery (46.1%), and rape (23.1%) are among the crimes experienced by the urban poor in the research region, according to the interviewees. Urbanization and its Consequences in the Transitional Rural Settlements of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria was the focus of Baadom, Amatari, and Derebeapade (2019). Data was gathered from secondary and primary sources, and descriptive statistical tools were used to examine it (Frequency distribution). The study examines the impacts of Yenagoa's unguided growth on the city's periphery settlements, which are seeing an increase in human population as a result of the city's unplanned growth. This has resulted in issues like as environmental craziness, rising occupancy rates, and potential human health risks.

Women's Empowerment and Poverty Reduction in Bangladeshi Rural Areas: A Focus on the Village Development Program was investigated by Nadim, Dwiyanto, and Nurlukman (2018).

The study's objectives were met using both primary and secondary data. The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square test. Women's empowerment has a significant impact on poverty reduction, according to the conclusions of the study. Despite this, the study's findings show that women have certain issues with empowerment. Poverty reduction also requires income-generating activities.

Table 2.1 Summary of Empirical Review

S/N	Author(s)	Year	Area of Study	Topic	Methodology	Findings
1	Wondimag egnhu	2012	Southern Ethiopia	Effects of rural-urban migration on rural households' income and poverty in Southern Ethiopia's Shebedino district	Cobb-Douglas production function model approach	The study found that migration has lowered the amount of available labor in rural areas dramatically.
2	Iyi	2014	Nigeria	A Review of Enugu (Enugu State, Nigeria) Urban Growth and Developm ent.	Percentage Score	The results of the research revealed that the identified indicators had a poor association.
3	Chukwued ozie and Ignatius	2014	Nigeria	Impact of rural-urban migration on rural livelihoods in the southeastern region of Nigeria.	Principal Component Analysis and the Livelihood Asset Indices approach	The results showed that there are regional differences in how migration affects people's means of subsistence.
4	Ademu	2015	Nigeria	Urbanization Problem and the Challenge of Youth Unemployem ent in Urban Centres in Nigeria	Percentage Score	It was of the opinion that Nigeria's urbanization and youth unemployment are a result of the economy's narrow base and unequal development between urban and rural areas.
5	Emodi and Emeka	2018	Nigeria	How urbanization in the Enugu metropolis has affected biodiversity	Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r) t-statistics.	The findings confirmed that urbanization has had an impact on the area's biodiversity, including the

				within the environment.		introduction of exotic species, over-exploitation of resources, habitat degradation, disease outbreaks, and species extinction.
6	Adejompo	2018	Ondo State, Nigeria	Urbanisation and Unemployment in IkareAkoko, Ondo State, Nigeria.	Ordinary least square (OLS)	The study found that urbanisation is widespread, which is a key source of unemployment. Infrastructure, trade and commerce, political causes, and the high birth rate are also other indicators of urbanisation.
7	Nadim, Dwiyanto and Nurlukman	2018	Bangladesh	Impact of Women Empowerment on Poverty Reduction in Rural Area of Bangladesh: Focusing on Village Development Program.	Chi-square test	Women's empowerment has a significant impact on poverty reduction, according to the conclusions of the study.
8	Ahmed &Suleman	2018	Nigeria	Impact of urbanization on economic growth in Nigeria	ADF and Phillips-Perron	The findings of the ARDL bounds testing revealed that GDP, unemployment, population, and fixed capital formation had a long-run relationship.
9	Baadam, Amatari & Derebeapade	2019	Bayelsa State, Nigeria.	Urbanization and its Consequences on the Transitional Rural	Frequency distribution	The study examines the impacts of Yenagoa's unguided growth on the city's periphery settlements, which

				Settlements of Yenagoa, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.		are seeing an increase in human population as a result of the city's unplanned growth.
10	Wizor & Le-ol	2020	Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria	Urbanization and Its Effects on Housing for the Urban Poor in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria	Mean Score	According to the findings of the inquiry, the bulk of the apartments occupied by the urban poor in the Uyo metropolitan are single rooms and self-contained apartments that are typically overcrowded.

Source: Author's Compilation, 2022.

2.4 Gap in Empirical Review

Although the majority of the empirical evaluation revealed that urbanization has a considerable impact on people's socioeconomic lives, the researcher highlighted certain research gaps. Iyi (2014) conducted an urban growth and development review in Enugu (Enugu State, Nigeria). Emodi and Emeka (2018) used Pearson's Product Moment to examine the way urbanization in the Enugu metropolis has impacted biodiversity in the environment; Adejomo (2018) used Ordinary least squares to investigate urbanization and unemployment in Ikare Akoko, Ondo State, Nigeria (OLS). Using the Cobb-Douglas production function model, Wondimagegnhu (2012) investigated the effects of rural-urban migration on rural household income and poverty in the Shebedino district in Southern Ethiopia. None of the research in the empirical evaluation focused on urbanization and employment opportunities in Enugu State, Nigeria. The study was conducted in seven (7) local governments of Enugu State urban areas utilizing descriptive survey research between 2016 and 2020. The data was gathered from primary and secondary sources, and the hypotheses were tested using Chi-Square Analysis. The current research will fill that need.

Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study used a survey design. The systematic collecting of data in a standardized format from a discernible population or representative is known as a descriptive survey research design (Oso & Onen, 2009). The decision to use this approach is supported by the fact that studying the entire population would have been extraordinarily challenging, if not impossible.

3.2 Sources of Data

The researcher utilized primary and secondary in the study.

Primary data: This involves the use of a questionnaire. A questionnaire was the major technique the researcher employed in this study to gather the initial data.

Secondary Sources of Data: These are the facts gathered from books and articles on the research and writings of other authors and researchers that are closely relevant to the study.

3.3 Area of the Study

The study was carried out in Enugu State. The study covered the following Local Government Areas: Enugu North, Enugu East, Enugu South, Nkanu West, Oji River, Nsukka and Udenue.

3.4 Population of the Study

The population of the study was 1,481,552. The population used for the study is presented in the table below.

Table 3.1: Population distribution of selected LGAs

LGA	Population	Percentage
Enugu North	242,140	16
Nkanu West	147,385	10
Udenu	178,687	12
Nsukka	309,448	21
Enugu East	277,119	19
Enugu South	198,032	13
Oji River	128,741	9
Total	1,481,552	100

Source: National Population Commission 2013 projected Census.

3.5 Determination of the Sample Size

Freund and William's (1986) statistical formula was used to obtain a sample size from a finite population. The formula was given thus:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 N p q}{N e^2 + Z^2 p q} \dots \dots \dots 1$$

Where;

n = Sample size, N = Population of the study, P = Probability of Success /Proportion

q = Probability of Failure /Proportion, Z = Standard error of the mean given under 96% reliability, e = Limit of tolerable sampling error, n = ?

N = 722,664, P =0.6, q = 1-p, z = 1.96, e = 4%

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2(1,481,552) (0.6)(0.4)}{1,481,552(0.04)^2 + (1.96)^2 (0.6) (0.4)} \quad n = \frac{3.8416 (1,481,552) (0.24)}{1,481,552(0.0016)+ (3.8416)(0.24)}$$

$$= \frac{1365967.239168}{2370.4832 + 0.921984} = \frac{1365967.239168}{2371.405184}$$

$$= 576.015, = \cong 576$$

3.6 Sampling Technique

A cluster sampling technique was used to carry out the study. In cluster sampling, the researcher separated the population into smaller groups known as clusters. Here, the researcher divided Enugu State into two, urban and rural. The researcher then randomly selected among these clusters (major urban cities: Enugu North, Nkanu West, Udenu, Nsukka, Enugu East, Enugu South and Oji River.)to form a sample. Cluster sampling was adopted because the large populations are widely geographically dispersed.From the cluster. From these, clusters, the researcher selected respondents who were relevant to the study, among them were: Community leaders, women organizations, development experts, employers of labour, government ministries in Enugu State etc.

3.7 Method of Data Collection

The instrument for data collection that was used is a close-ended questionnaire.The questionnaire was distributed directly to respondents to complete. The questionnaire was drawn in Likert scale format. This Likert scale format is a choice from strongly disagree to strongly agree with the statement.

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

The Instrument was submitted to five specialists in the field of Operations management and measurement experts at Enugu State University of Science and Technology. The professionals were requested to examine the items in the instrument and decidewhether the items would be suitable for the information it was designed to elicit.

3.9 Reliability of the Instrument

The instrument was additionally subjected to Cronbach's alpha. All variables were reliable as their Cronbach's alpha was greater than 0.7. The Cronbach alpha of 0.81 was obtained.

3.10 Methods of Data Analyses

The collected data from the survey questionnaire were transformed into useful information, through the use of mean score while Chi-square Analysis with the use of SPSS 23.0 was used to test the hypotheses.

The chi-square test tool was employed to test the hypotheses. $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$

Where O = Observed frequency, E = Expected frequency

Assumptions: Level of significance = 0.05

Decision Rule:

1. Reject H_0 if the P-Value $\text{cal} < 0.05$ at a 5% level of significance.
2. Otherwise, accept the null hypothesis (H_0).

Data Presentation and Analysis

4.1 Data Presentation and Analysis

In this section, all the data collected from the respondents through the questionnaire were presented and analysis followed respectively. Descriptive Analysis and Chi-square Test Analysis. Out of 576 copies of a questionnaire distributed, 518 were returned but 500 copies were found useful for the study.

4.2 Analysis of Data

Research Question One: What is the influence of the increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?

Table 4.1: Influence of increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state

s/n	Response	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Decision
1	The mass movement to the cities and towns lead to a population explosion which contributes to the unemployment situation	151	189	20	10	40	500	3.6	Accepted
2	The urban centres could not accommodate the influx of people	169	211	10	70	40	500	3.8	Accepted
3	Youths relocate to cities in the hopes of finding lucrative work	191	159	10	90	50	500	3.7	Accepted
4	Through a significant and quick rise in the labor force, the movement has an impact on the supply side.	172	189	10	88	41	500	3.7	Accepted
5	The rapid expansion of the labor force is a result of the high population growth rate.	181	139	21	11	40	500	3.6	Accepted
Grand Mean								3.68	

Source: Field Survey 2022

The responses as presented in Table 4.1 indicate descriptive statistics on the influence of increased population rate on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. All the items 1-5 in descriptive statistics were affirmed by the respondents. The respondents generally agreed that there is the effect of a high population growth rate on the unemployment rate in Nigerian states. The Grand Mean of 3.68 is a strong indication that the

respondents are firm in their conviction that the high population growth rate affected the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of the concentration of development activities in urban centres on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?

Table 4.2: The influence of concentration of development activities in urban centres on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state

s/n	Response	SA	A	U	D	SD	Total	Mean	Decision
1	The concentration of social amenities in the urban centers while rural areas are neglected	20	162	10	59	61	500	3.8	Accepted
2	Inequality of income between urban and rural dwellers due to the concentration of development activities	16	149	11	12	50	500	3.5	Accepted
3	The rapid concentration of educational institutions in urban centres affects the unemployment rate in Nigeria	16	180	9	81	70	500	3.6	Accepted
4	High rural-urban drift in Nigeria because of the inequalities, in terms of infrastructural facilities	17	133	17	10	70	500	3.4	Accepted
5	The rural areas in Nigeria are regions of the backward and depressed homogenous economy	15	165	16	11	47	500	3.5	Accepted
Grand Mean								3.56	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.2 is assumed to be indicative responses to the extent to which the concentration of development activities in urban centres influenced employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. The grand mean of 3.56 of the study affirms that the respondents strongly agreed with the question asked.

Research Question Three: In what way has the existence of higher education influenced the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?

Table 4.3: The extent the existence of higher education has influenced the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state?

s/n	Response	SA	A	D	DA	SD	FRE	Mean	Decision
1	The rapid expansion of the educational system leads to an increase in the supply of educated manpower	179	189	18	71	43	500	3.8	Accepted
2	The increasing demand for higher education has been the problem of suitable employment	179	175	16	79	51	500	3.7	Accepted
3	The demand for white-collar jobs by graduate contribute to a high rate of unemployment	188	162	10	83	57	500	3.6	Accepted
4	Poor quality training from education institutions affects the employability of graduates of higher institutions in Nigeria	186	164	16	79	55	500	3.7	Accepted
5	The desire for the certificate (certificate disease syndrome) often leads to neglect of technical skills needed for self-sustainability and self-employment	167	180	21	93	39	500	3.7	Accepted
Grand Mean								3.7	

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Table 4.3 is indicative responses to ways in which the existence of higher education influenced employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state with a mean score of above 3.0. The grand mean of 3.7 affirms the fact that the growth of higher education influenced employment opportunities in Enugu state.

4.3 Testing of Research Hypotheses

The chi-square test tool was employed to test the hypotheses. $\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$

Where O = Observed frequency, E = Expected frequency

Assumptions: Level of significance = 0.05

Decision Rule:

- 3. Reject Ho if the P-Value cal < 0.05 at a 5% level of significance.
- 4. Otherwise, accept the null hypothesis (Ho).

4.3.1 Test of hypotheses one

Restatement of hypothesis one

Ho: Increased population rate has no significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

Table 4.3: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	226.826 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	280.891	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	20.659	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	500		

a. 7 cells (28.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.69.

Source: Author's compilation SPSS 23.0 Result Output

We reject the null hypothesis, which states that the two variables are independent of one another, in this case because the p -value.000 is less than the typical α .0.05 value.

Simply put, the outcome is noteworthy - the data indicate that the increased population rate had a significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

Test of hypotheses Two

Restatement of hypothesis Two

Ho: Concentration of development activities in urban centres has no significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

Table 4.4: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	109.894 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	131.917	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.128	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	500		

a. 9 cells (36.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is 1.48.

Source: Author's compilation SPSS 23.0 Result Output

The p -value of .000 is lesser than the standard α value of 0.05, so we reject the null hypothesis. To put it simply, the result is *significant* – the data submits that the variables; Concentration of development activities in urban centres have a significant influence on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

Test of hypotheses Three

Restatement of hypothesis Three

Ho: The existence of higher education has no significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state

Table 4.13: Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	148.616 ^a	16	.000
Likelihood Ratio	166.369	16	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	2.346	1	.126
N of Valid Cases	500		

a. 12 cells (48.0%) have an expected count of less than 5. The minimum expected count is .67.

Source: Author's compilation SPSS 23.0 Result Output

We reject the null hypothesis, which states that the two variables are independent of one another, in this case because the p -value of.000 is less than the conventional α value of 0.05. Simply put, the outcome is noteworthy - the data indicate that the Existence of higher education had a significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis found that the increased population rate had a considerable impact on urban dwellers' employment options in Enugu state. The estimated significance of $2 = 226.826$ is bigger than the table value of $2 = 9.95$, according to the chi-square test. This finding is consistent with Wizer & Le-(2020) ol's findings, which revealed that residences are overcrowded and that rapid population growth hinders employment chances.

The estimated value of $\chi^2 = 109.894$ is bigger than the table value of $\chi^2 = 9.95$, according to the chi-square test. The statistical significance revealed that the concentration of development activities in urban areas had a considerable impact on urban people's employment chances in Enugu state. This study is consistent with Njoku & Chikere (2015), who showed that limited economic possibilities in rural areas, inadequate social infrastructure in rural communities, and a desire to escape the unattractive aspect of rural places all contribute to rural-urban migration.

The existence of higher education has a major impact on employment chances for urban people in Enugu state, according to hypothesis three. Mohamed, Youssef, Nguyen-Viet, and Agnès (2014), reported that rapid development of the educational system immediately leads to a rise in the supply of educated workforce above the matching demand for them, which contributes to Nigeria's young unemployment crisis.

5.1 Summary of Findings

The following were the findings from the study:

- i. The findings revealed that the increased population rate had a significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. It meant that Nigeria's fast urbanization, and the resulting growth of the urban population, had not been matched by a proportional change in social, economic, or technological development.
- ii. The concentration of development activities in urban centres had a significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. It suggested that limited economic possibilities in rural areas, a lack of social infrastructure in rural areas, and a desire to escape the unattractive/dull aspect of rural areas were all factors driving rural-urban movement.
- iii. The existence of higher education had a significant effect on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu state. It meant that the quick expansion of the educational system resulted in an increase in the supply of educated workers exceeding the demand for them, leading to Nigeria's young unemployment problem.

5.2 Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is affirmed that rapid urbanization, particularly the rise of large cities, and the associated difficulties of unemployment, poverty, insufficient healthcare, poor sanitation, urban slums, and environmental degradation constitute a formidable challenge in developing countries. It can be concluded that urbanization had a significant influence on the employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu State.

5.3 Recommendations

The following recommendations were made:

- i. The study recommended that government should make provision for the rapid development of rural communities in Enugu State as this will help to curb rural-urban migration and control the high population growth rate in the urban centers.
- ii. It is recommended that the Enugu State government should embark on adequate providing basic infrastructure, services, and social amenities (such as providing rural communities with schools, water supplies, safe roads, health facilities, steady electricity, and other amenities) This will automatically stop the rural-urban drift by lowering the level of inequality between urban areas and rural areas.
- iii. Government should relocate most of the existing higher institutions in the Enugu metropolis to rural communities to reduce the high population of students in the urban centers so that the existing public infrastructure in the city centers will not be over-stressed. The community leaders and Local Government council should make land available for the siting of higher institutions in the rural areas.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The study contributed to a good understanding of the dynamics of urbanization on employment opportunities of urban dwellers in Enugu State. The study offers the model which should be adopted in the analysis of the high

population growth rate, the concentration of development activities in urban centres and the rapid growth of formal education all of which influence the urban dwellers.

The study equally offers insight to policymakers that Population growth needs to be checked through Family Planning as overpopulation has serious negative consequences on the state and the country at large.

The study has highlighted the need for the Government to focus on the rural areas for development activities such as providing electricity, good roads, Tertiary Institutions and siting up Government Ministries, this will encourage people to live in such areas and decongest the urban areas.

Finally, the study will be of immense benefit to Urban Administrators concerning Urban Planning and Management.

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